

ON THREE CONSECUTIVE PAIRS OF LUCAS AND FIBONACCI NUMBERS
CONNECTED TO PELL-LUCAS AND PELL POLYNOMIALS

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ABSTRACT. In the present paper we connect three consecutive pairs of Lucas and Fibonacci numbers, namely, $\{(L_{3n}, F_{3n}), (L_{3n+1}, F_{3n+1}), (L_{3n+2}, F_{3n+2}) : n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$ to Pell-Lucas and Pell polynomials, namely,

$$P_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} \left[(x + \sqrt{x^2 + 1})^n + (x - \sqrt{x^2 + 1})^n \right] \text{ and}$$

$$Q_n(x) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x^2 + 1}} \left[(x + \sqrt{x^2 + 1})^n - (x - \sqrt{x^2 + 1})^n \right].$$

We work out some interesting combinatorial identities of $X_n = P_n(2), Y_n = Q_n(2)$ and the three consecutive pairs of Lucas and Fibonacci numbers.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In [1], a pair of sequences (x_n, y_n) is introduced by evaluating the well known Tchebyshev polynomials of first and second kind, namely,

$$T_n(x) = \frac{1}{2} \left[(x + \sqrt{x^2 - 1})^n + (x - \sqrt{x^2 - 1})^n \right] \text{ and}$$

$$U_n(x) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x^2 - 1}} \left[(x + \sqrt{x^2 - 1})^{n+1} - (x - \sqrt{x^2 - 1})^{n+1} \right],$$

$n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$ at $x = 9$.

The six consecutive pairs of Lucas and Fibonacci numbers, namely, $\{(L_{6n+k}, F_{6n+k}) : k = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ and $n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$ have beautiful connection to (x_n, y_n) given by

$$L_{6n+k} = L_k x_n + 20 F_k y_n$$

$$F_{6n+k} = F_k x_n + 4 L_k y_n,$$

$k = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ and $n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$.

Some interesting combinatorial identities of (x_n, y_n) and (L_{6n+k}, F_{6n+k}) are presented there [1].

Motivated strongly by the above paper, first we discovered one more simple and beautiful connection between (L_{3n}, F_{3n}) and $(P_n(2), Q_n(2))$, namely,

$$L_{3n} = (2 + \sqrt{5})^n + (2 - \sqrt{5})^n$$

$$= (2 + \sqrt{2^2 + 1})^n + (2 - \sqrt{2^2 + 1})^n$$

$$= 2 P_n(2)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} F_{3n} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} \left[(2 + \sqrt{5})^n - (2 - \sqrt{5})^n \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^2 + 1}} \left[(2 + \sqrt{2^2 + 1})^n - (2 - \sqrt{2^2 + 1})^n \right] \\ &= 2 Q_n(2). \end{aligned}$$

We introduce, $X_n = P_n(2)$ and $Y_n = Q_n(2)$. Then they fit so well that one may derive

$$\begin{aligned} L_{3n+k} &= L_k X_n + 5 F_k Y_n \\ F_{3n+k} &= F_k X_n + L_k Y_n \\ k &= 0, 1, 2, 3 \text{ and } n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \end{aligned}$$

In the present paper, we derive some interesting combinatorial identities of (X_n, Y_n) and (L_{3n+k}, F_{3n+k}) . The study of combinatorial identities have many interesting facets and applications available in the recent literature. One can find combinatorial identities of the following entities-

- (i) Catalan numbers [2, 3]
- (ii) Lucas and Fibonacci Numbers [1, 7, 10, 11, 13, 15]
- (iii) Tchebyshev Polynomials [1, 3-6, 8]
- (iv) Pell - Lucas and Pell polynomials [8, 14]
- (v) Brahmagupta polynomials [9, 12]

The number theory of L_n and F_n enables one to derive many Combinatorial identities mentioned in the end of the above paragraph.

2. RECURRENCE RELATIONS

For the sake of smooth computation of $\{(L_{3n+k}, F_{3n+k}) : k = 0, 1, 2, 3 \text{ and } n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$, a pair of sequences, namely (X_n, Y_n) described by Pell-Lucas and Pell polynomials is extensively applied.

Definition:

$$X_n = P_n(2), Y_n = Q_n(2) \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

The pair (X_n, Y_n) has the following binet form :

$$\begin{aligned} X_n &= \frac{1}{2} [\zeta^n + \eta^n] \\ Y_n &= \frac{\zeta^n - \eta^n}{\zeta - \eta} \end{aligned}$$

where $\zeta = 2 + \sqrt{5}$, $\eta = 2 - \sqrt{5}$ and $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$.

ζ and η satisfy the following relations : $\zeta + \eta = 4$, $\zeta - \eta = 2\sqrt{5}$, $\zeta \eta = -1$. By applying above binet form, one can show that (X_n, Y_n) satisfy the following relations which are directed by Pell-Lucas and Pell polynomials [8, 14].

Identities 2.1

$$\begin{aligned} (1) \quad X_{n+1} &= 4 X_n + X_{n-1} \\ &= \frac{Y_{n+2} + Y_n}{2} \\ &= 2 X_n + 5 Y_n \\ (2) \quad Y_{n+1} &= 4 Y_n + Y_{n-1} \\ &= \frac{X_{n+2} + X_n}{10} \\ &= X_n + 2 Y_n \end{aligned}$$

$$n = 1, 2, 3 \dots$$

Identities 2.2

$$\begin{aligned}
 (1) \quad 2 L_{3n+k} &= L_{3n} L_k + 5 F_{3n} F_k \\
 (2) \quad 2 F_{3n+k} &= L_{3n} F_k + F_{3n} L_k \\
 (3) \quad L_{3n+k} &= L_k X_n + 5 F_k Y_n \\
 &= (L_k - 2 F_k) X_n + F_k X_{n+1} \\
 &= (5 F_k - 2 L_k) Y_n + L_k Y_{n+1} \\
 (4) \quad F_{3n+k} &= F_k X_n + L_k Y_n \\
 &= \frac{(5 F_k - 2 L_k) X_n + L_k X_{n+1}}{5} \\
 &= (L_k - 2 F_k) Y_n + F_k Y_{n+1}
 \end{aligned}$$

$k = 0, 1, 2, 3$ and $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

Identities 2.3

$$\begin{aligned}
 (1) \quad L_{3(n+1)+k} &= 4 L_{3n+k} + L_{3(n-1)+k} \\
 (2) \quad F_{3(n+1)+k} &= 4 F_{3n+k} + F_{3(n-1)+k}
 \end{aligned}$$

$k = 3, 4, 5$ and $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

Identities 2.4

$$\begin{aligned}
 (1) \quad 2 L_{3n+1} &= L_{3n+3} - L_{3n} \\
 (2) \quad 2 F_{3n+1} &= F_{3n+3} - F_{3n} \\
 (3) \quad 2 L_{3n+2} &= L_{3n+3} + L_{3n} \\
 (4) \quad 2 F_{3n+2} &= F_{3n+3} + F_{3n} \\
 (5) \quad L_{3n+3} &= 2 L_{3n} + 5 F_{3n} \\
 (6) \quad F_{3n+3} &= L_{3n} + 2 F_{3n} \\
 (7) \quad 2 L_{3n+4} &= 3 L_{3n+3} + L_{3n} \\
 (8) \quad 2 F_{3n+4} &= 3 F_{3n+3} + F_{3n} \\
 (9) \quad 2 L_{3n-1} &= L_{3n+3} - 3 L_{3n} \\
 (10) \quad 2 F_{3n-1} &= F_{3n+3} - 3 F_{3n}
 \end{aligned}$$

$n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

3. MATRIX POWER IDENTITIES, CASSINI DETERMINANT IDENTITIES AND GENERATING FUNCTIONS

In the literature, a matrix power identity called Brahmagupta power identity ([9], [12]) is described

$$\begin{bmatrix} \alpha_n & \beta_n \\ t \beta_n & \alpha_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha & \beta \\ t \beta & \alpha \end{bmatrix}^n$$

for

$$\begin{aligned}
 \alpha_n &= \frac{1}{2} \left[(\alpha + \beta\sqrt{t})^n + (\alpha - \beta\sqrt{t})^n \right] \\
 \beta_n &= \frac{1}{2\sqrt{t}} \left[(\alpha + \beta\sqrt{t})^n - (\alpha - \beta\sqrt{t})^n \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

When $\alpha = 2$, $\beta = 1$ and $t = 5$ we obtain X_n and Y_n . As a consequence we have the following matrix power identities and Cassini determinant identities described in the following results

Identities 3.1

$$\begin{aligned}
 (1) \quad & \begin{bmatrix} X_n & Y_n \\ 5 Y_n & X_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ 5 & 2 \end{bmatrix}^n \\
 (2) \quad & \begin{bmatrix} Y_{n-1} & Y_n \\ Y_n & Y_{n+1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 4 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 4 \end{bmatrix}^{n-1} \\
 (3) \quad & \begin{bmatrix} X_{n-1} & X_n \\ X_n & X_{n+1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 \\ 2 & 9 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 4 \end{bmatrix}^{n-1} \\
 & n = 1, 2, 3, \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

Identities 3.2

$$\begin{aligned}
 (1) \quad & X_n^2 - 5 Y_n^2 = (-1)^n \\
 (2) \quad & Y_{n-1} Y_{n+1} - Y_n^2 = (-1)^n \\
 (3) \quad & X_{n-1} X_{n+1} - X_n^2 = (-1)^{n-1} 5 \\
 & n = 1, 2, 3, \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

Identities 3.3

$$\begin{bmatrix} L_{3n+k} & F_{3n+k} \\ 5 F_{3n+k} & L_{3n+k} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} L_k & F_k \\ 5 F_k & L_k \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ 5 & 2 \end{bmatrix}^n$$

$k = 0, 1, 2, 3$ and $n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$

Next we state the generating function of X_n, Y_n, L_{3n+k} and $F_{3n+k}, k = 0, 1, 2, 3$ with the help of the identities given by (2.1) and (2.2).

Identities 3.4

$$\begin{aligned}
 (1) \quad & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} L_{3n+k} t^n = \frac{L_k + (L_{k+3} - 4 L_k) t}{1 - 4t - t^2} \\
 (2) \quad & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} F_{3n+k} t^n = \frac{F_k + (F_{k+3} - 4 F_k) t}{1 - 4t - t^2} \\
 (3) \quad & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} X_n t^n = \frac{1 - 2t}{1 - 4t - t^2} \\
 (4) \quad & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} Y_n t^n = \frac{t}{1 - 4t - t^2} \\
 & k = 0, 1, 2, 3.
 \end{aligned}$$

4. SUMMATION IDENTITIES

By suitable rearranging recurrence relations one like below the summation identities can be derived non trivially.

$$X_k = 4 X_{k-1} + X_{k-2}, \quad k = 2, 3, \dots, n$$

Adding all and simplifying we get the following summation identities:

Identities 4.1

$$\begin{aligned}
 (1) \quad & 4 \sum_{k=0}^n X_k = X_{n+1} + X_n + 1 \\
 (2) \quad & 4 \sum_{k=0}^n Y_k = Y_{n+1} + Y_n - 1 \\
 & n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

Following the same ideas, one can derive the following summation identities :

Identities 4.2

$$(1) \quad 4 \sum_{k=0}^n X_{2k} = X_{2n+1} + 2$$

$$(2) \quad 4 \sum_{k=0}^n Y_{2k} = Y_{2n+1} - 1$$

$n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$

The binet form of X_n and Y_n will guide the following square sum identities:

Identities 4.3

$$(1) \quad \sum_{k=0}^n X_k^2 = \frac{1}{32} [X_{2n+2} - X_{2n}] + \left[\frac{2 + (-1)^n}{4} \right]$$

$$(2) \quad \sum_{k=0}^n Y_k^2 = \frac{1}{160} [(X_{2n+2} - X_{2n}) - \frac{(-1)^n}{20}]$$

$n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$

By making use of $L_{3n+k} = L_k X_n + 5 F_k Y_n$ and $F_{3n+k} = F_k X_n + L_k Y_n : k = 0, 1, 2, 3$. One can directly derive the following square sum identities :

Identities 4.4

$$(1) \quad \sum_{r=0}^n L_{3r+k}^2 = \frac{L_{2k}}{80} [X_{2n+2} - X_{2n}] + \frac{F_{2k}}{4} [Y_{2n+1} - 1] + \frac{F_k^2}{4} - \frac{(-1)^{n+k}}{5}$$

$$(2) \quad \sum_{r=0}^n F_{3r+k}^2 = \frac{L_{2k}}{16} [X_{2n+2} - X_{2n}] + \frac{5 F_{2k}}{4} [Y_{2n+1} - 1] + \frac{L_k^2}{4} + (-1)^{n+k}$$

$k = 0, 1, 2, 3$ and $n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$

5. CONVOLUTION IDENTITIES

The binet forms will guide the following convolution identities :

Identities 5.1

$$(1) \quad \sum_{k=0}^n X_k X_{n-k} = \frac{1}{2} [(n+1)X_n + Y_{n+1}]$$

$$(2) \quad \sum_{k=0}^n Y_k Y_{n-k} = \frac{1}{10} [(n+1)X_n - Y_{n+1}]$$

$$(3) \quad \sum_{k=0}^n X_k Y_{n-k} = \sum_{k=0}^n Y_k X_{n-k} = \left(\frac{n+1}{2} \right) Y_n$$

$n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

Identities 5.2

$$(1) \quad \sum_{r=0}^n L_{3r+k} L_{3(n-r)+k} = (n+1) L_{3n+2k} + (-1)^k 2 Y_{n+1}$$

$$(2) \quad \sum_{r=0}^n F_{3r+k} F_{3(n-r)+k} = \frac{1}{5} [(n+1) L_{3n+2k} - (-1)^k 2 Y_{n+1}]$$

$$(3) \quad \sum_{r=0}^n L_{3r+k} F_{3(n-r)+k} = \sum_{r=0}^n F_{3r+k} L_{3(n-r)+k} = (n+1) F_{3n+2k}$$

$k = 0, 1, 2, 3$ and $n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$

The identities 5.1 and 5.2 can be derived directly using the identities of the section (2). For a good account of convolution identities one may refer to [2].

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